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Sample Name: Proszki

Si 7h

eZAF Quant Result - Analysis Uncertainty: 16.16 %

Element	Weight %	MDL	Atomic %	Error %
C K	29.4	0.10	47.9	10.1
O K	5.5	0.04	6.7	7.4
Si K	65.1	0.07	45.3	5.6

/Lukasiewicz 25.02.25/Proszki/Si 7h/Full Area 1/

kV: 5 Mag: 500 Takeoff: 35.6 Live Time(s): 300 Amp Time(μs): 0.96 Resolution:(eV) 131.6

Det: Element-C2B